

Simple interference based colorization of Si based solar cells and panels with ITO/SiN_x:H double layer antireflective coatings

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Abstract

The integration of solar modules into buildings offers a highly attractive area for an enlargement of the market for commercial solar cells. Therefore, cost-effective industrial approaches to fabricated solar cells and relevant modules with different colors are required. In this work a simple method for applying individual color to Si based solar cells was adapted to the industrially fabricated commercial cells with standard SiN_x:H antireflection coating (ARC) and also explicitly described by a fundamental model. This method of coloring is based on the optical interference effect in the layered structure. The structure includes a thin indium tin oxide (ITO) layer deposited on the top of the ARC. An intentional change of the ITO thickness from 0 to 240 nm resulted in a change of the color through the visible spectrum. The color was added to multi- as well as mono-Si based industrially fabricated textured solar cells with conventional blue color ARC. Reasonable agreement between the theoretical and experimental results has been obtained from the model calculations. For the proof of concept, a mini-solar-module with six green cells was fabricated that were coated by an ITO (185 nm)/SiN_x:H double layer ARC stack. It is shown that efficiency of such module is only about 1.5% lower than that for the mini-module manufactured using reference industrial cells with SiN_x:H ARC only. It is concluded that the proposed approach can be considered as a cost-effective method to fabricate coloured Si based cells and relevant modules using only one simple technological step.

Keywords: colored solar cells/modules, c-Si silicon solar cells, double layer antireflective coatings, ITO, Building integrated photovoltaics.

1. Introduction

Building integrated photovoltaics (BIPV) has recently attracted a high interest from the developers because of several reasons: (i) according to the International Energy Agency, 32% of overall energy usage is accounted for by buildings and this suggests that the development of net-zero buildings can be a smart decision [1]; (ii) buildings provide huge amount of available area for PV installations. Moreover, BIPV combines the electricity generation and consumption at the same place, which significantly reduces the transportation and transformation losses. According to the BIPV sector

growth forecast issued by n-tech Research, the BIPV is expected to reach 13% of the total PV market until 2022 [2].

Silicon has a huge part (up to about 93%) of the global PV market [3]. Despite of this, the massive industrial fabrication of Si based cells is still limited to two main colors, namely blue and black, which strongly limits the architectural freedom. The design of roof modules clearly requires more choices of BIPV cell colors [4].

It should be noted that several modern solar cell technologies had already introduced the fabrication of colored solar cells, including quantum dot solar cells [5], dye sensitized solar cells [6], perovskite solar cells [7], organic/polymer solar cells [8]. Moreover, there are some attempts to colorize the CIGS [9] and a-Si:H [10] based solar cells. However, the colored cells and modules are commercial products with no essential impact on the PV market. In addition, the progress in commercialization of the colored solar cells is limited due to significantly lower efficiencies and stability compared to the Si based products.

The silicon solar cell technology can already provide several options for colored cells and modules. The most common and straightforward approach to change the color of the Si based solar cells is based on the variation of the ARC, which can be done during the solar cell manufacturing process [11]. Recently, a promising solution was proposed by Soman and Antony [12] for large scale modules with photonic crystal structures. In this solution, the silicon nitride ($\text{SiN}_x\text{:H}$) and silicon oxynitride (SiO_xN_y) dielectric layers with varying compositions and thicknesses were used to obtain the selective light reflection. However, a modification of the ARC thickness and compositions requires sufficiently large changes in the solar cell manufacturing processes. Such modifications typically are not very attractive to the PV industry especially considering the fact that the efficiency of the colored solar cells is obviously lower than that of standard Si cells [13–15]. Therefore, approaches, which can provide processing of colored Si based cells without interfering with the solar cell manufacturing process are of the great interest.

One of the cost-effective approaches, which can be used to modify color of Si based solar cells with standard $\text{SiN}_x\text{:H}$ ARC is based on implementation of a double antireflection coating (DLARC) that includes an additional layer on the top of the fully finished solar cells [16]. Simulations were carried out for the solar cells with $\text{MgF}_2/\text{SiN}_x\text{:H}$, $\text{SiO}_2/\text{SiN}_x\text{:H}$ and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{SiN}_x\text{:H}$ DLARCs. It has been concluded that, for the cells with the optimized DLARC, the current densities can be higher than in the solar cells with the conventional $\text{SiN}_x\text{:H}$ single layer anti-reflection coating (SLARC). Moreover, Li et. al reported simulation results for solar cells with $\text{SiO}_2/\text{SiN}_x\text{:H}$ DLARC ARC [13]. Obtained results demonstrated that DLARC is better for color modification versus SLARC, since implementation of DLARC can lead to a reduction of the current losses in some special cases. However, the SiO_2 layer is not the best choice for DLARC cells because its refractive index is very similar to ethylene vinyl acetate (EVA) ($n \approx 1.5$) that is mostly used for the module encapsulation in the PV industry. Zeng et. al [14] addressed this issue by using the $\text{SiO}_x\text{N}_y/\text{SiN}_x\text{:H}$ DLARC. In this approach, the $\text{SiN}_x\text{:H}$ (the refractive index $n = 2.05$ and the thickness $d = 80$ nm) was covered with a varying thickness of the SiO_xN_y film ($n = 1.8$). The resulting cells have no additional current density improvement with increasing SiO_xN_y thickness, but obtained colors were quite similar to the case of SLARC.

It should be noted that the main requirement for DLARC structures is to provide antireflection properties, which can be done, if refractive index of the top layer is lower than that of the bottom one, but higher than that of an encapsulation layer. As in case of SLARC, not only complex refractive index

and thickness must be optimized for color and efficiency, but passivation properties of coating should be maintained, while in DLARC structures, top layer can be varied without affecting passivation properties of the bottom layer- Si interface. Efficiency and color of DLARC structure is a complex function of dielectric functions of ARC layers, their thicknesses and cell surface morphology defined by texturization. Detailed analysis of the optical properties of DLARC is performed in Sections 2.3 and 3.2.

There were no detailed studies found focused on solar cells with DLARC, which includes an ITO based outer layer. DLARC with an ITO film is worthy to investigate since ITO films are stable and, as a transparent conductive oxide (TCO), frequently used for the transparent conductive contacts. In addition, it is quite easy to modify the optical properties of ITO by variation of the deposition parameters. In particular, Pour and Shafai [17], have demonstrated that the refractive index of ITO can be intentionally changed from $n = 1.69$ to $n=2.1$ at 632 nm by the modification of the stoichiometry and the crystalline structure of the film. Metal oxide film structure and its effect on dielectric function were described in more detail by Ohring Milton [18]. Moreover, in combination with high electrical conductance, the ITO is highly attractive for the formation of DLARC which, in addition, potentially can reduce the charge collection losses in the contacts and allow the busbar soldering after the ITO deposition.

In this paper the DLARCs were formed by deposition of an additional ITO layer on the top of commercial Si based solar cells (both monocrystalline and multi-crystalline) with conventional SiNx:H ARC, which were cut by laser to reduced sizes (squares with surface area of 61.43 cm^2). Reduced sizes were defined by the homogeneity requirements for the ITO deposition. ITO was deposited using magnetron sputtering technique, a method which is frequently used in glass industry for large area deposition of the IR reflection, EMC shielding or other electro-optical coatings based on ITO layers. We also carried out numerical simulations on the basis of an optical reflection model.

2. Materials and methods

Three sets of initial samples were prepared for this study: (a) bare glass plates, (b) multicrystalline silicon solar cells and (c) monocrystalline silicon solar cells.

The multicrystalline solar cell samples were prepared by laser cutting. For this, the standard $157.5 \times 157.5 \text{ mm}$ 4 busbar solar cells with the efficiency of 18.4% were cut to 4 equal parts with the dimensions $78.38 \text{ mm} \times 78.38 \text{ mm}$. The monocrystalline based samples with the same dimensions were similarly cut from the 3 busbar cells avoiding pseudo-rectangular corners. The sample preparation method is illustrated in [Figure 1](#).

RF magnetron sputtering was used for the deposition of thin ITO layers on top of soda lime glass substrates and Si based solar cells with standard SiN_x:H ARC. The depositions were done at room temperature. Upon deposition RF magnetron power was P=100 W and the pressure of the process gas Ar in the deposition chamber was p=5·10⁻³ mbar. An ITO target of diameter 4 inches was used as the sputtering source.

Figure 1. Commercial 18.4% polycrystalline solar cell with cutting track marked in yellow and resulting cell dimensions.

Thickness of ITO layers in ITO/glass reference structures was measured using the Dektak 150 contact stylus profilometer. Measured thickness was fit linearly to obtain the calibration diagram (see Figure 2).

The multicrystalline silicon based samples with ITO/SiN_x:H DLARC were used to fabricated test mini-modules to estimate an influence of the introduced color (green) on the module efficiency. Two solar modules, reference (blue color) and green color module each with 6 cells with dimensions 78.38 x 78.38 mm have been fabricated. The cells were connected sequentially and sandwiched between the EVA sheets and glass in the sample modules.

The deposition duration was varied in the range from 225 s to 2362.5 s in steps of 112.5 s. to obtain ITO films with different thicknesses. For this, the experimental relationship between the deposition duration and the film thicknesses was obtained during a special calibration routine.

Figure 2. Measured (data points) and linearly fit (red line) data of ITO thickness dependence on the deposition time.

2.1 Characterization

The optical reflection and the external quantum efficiency (*EQE*) spectra were measured by a Bentham PVE 300 spectrometer with a lock-in amplifier. Xenon and halogen lamps mix was used for the radiation source. A TMC300 monochromator was used to vary the wavelength of the incident light from 300 to 1200 nm. The illumination spot was homogeneous and limited within the area between the metal contacts of the solar cell samples and, therefore, the contact area was excluded from the model calculations.

Calculation of photo generated short circuit current density was performed using the following formula:

$$J_{sc} = \frac{q}{hc} \int_{300}^{1200} T(\lambda)I(\lambda)IQE(\lambda) \lambda d\lambda, \quad (1)$$

where $I(\lambda)$ – incident radiance (W·cm⁻²·nm⁻¹), $IQE(\lambda)$ – internal quantum efficiency, $T(\lambda)$ – transmittance, q – elementary charge (C), h – Planck's constant (J·s), c – speed of light (cm·s⁻¹).

The module *IV* characteristics were measured using a PASAN highlight 3, AAA+ class solar simulator with the world PV scale standard (WPVS) monitor cell.

2.2 Numerical experiment

The front surface optical characteristics were obtained from the numerical simulation of a model sample cell using the OPAL 2 tool created by the Australian company “PV Lighthouse Pty. Ltd” [19]. This freeware program uses the ray tracing to determine the set of unique paths that the incident light follows.

For the simulations the AM 1.5g solar spectrum was used. The standard silicon solar cell structure with 200 μm thickness [20] and the surface texturization similar to the random upward pyramids with characteristic angle of 54.74° have been used for simulations. On the top of such structure $\text{SiN}_x\text{:H}$ ARC layer with 80 nm thickness has been introduced in the model. The dispersion was taken from [21]. According to S. Duttagupta et. al, the real part of the refractive index was set to $n=2.03$ at 632 nm.

The second antireflective layer in the simulation model was an indium tin oxide film. The second antireflective layer in the simulation model of DLARC structure was an indium tin oxide film. It should be noted that although spectroscopic ellipsometry characterization of ARC films on textured multicrystalline and monocrystalline silicon solar is possible [22], however steps, which have to be taken to align the pyramids facets perpendicular to the plane of incidence of the ellipsometer are quite sophisticated and moreover such alignment can't be done in simple way, if textures are more complicated than the pyramids. According this research team, such approach never was demonstrated for DLARC structures and more complex textures apart pyramid-like and requires special efforts and calibration. Therefore, to study the main trends concerning the evolution of the reflection properties of ITO/ SiN_x DLARC upon variation of the ITO layer thickness, three different complex refractive index spectra, named as ITO1, ITO2 and ITO3. As a result, results presented below, should be considered as indicative and should be used for the general relative analysis with experimental data obtained for the colorization of solar cells using ITO/ SiN_x DLARC.

Parameters for ITO1 and ITO2 spectra were taken from Z. Holman work [23], where an ITO film was grown by a DC magnetron sputtering with electron concentrations $n=0.17\text{e-}20\text{ cm}^{-3}$ and $n=4.9\text{e-}20\text{ cm}^{-3}$ and real refractive indexes $n=2.07$ and $n=1.80$ at 630nm (respectively). The Tauc-Lorentz-Drude model was used for the dielectric function approximation. Parameters for ITO3 were taken from Robert and Jacob work, where they used the Drude model for the fitting of the measured ellipsometry data [24]. In this study a commercial ITO film from Optics Balzers with the thickness of 17 nm on glass was analyzed. The electron concentration was $n = 6.2 \cdot 10^{-20}\text{ cm}^{-3}$. ITO3 data was extrapolated linearly from 400 – 1200 nm to 300 - 1200nm (using 401 and 405 nm wavelength values).

In simulations of this model the ITO thickness was varied from 0 to 210 nm and dependences of the reflectance spectrum and J_{sc} current were obtained.

2.3 Fundamental aspects of the model

The light refraction in the two layer model was described by the Fresnel equations. The incident light is partially reflected from the top surface, the first interface boundary between the first and the second layers and the bottom interface between the second layer and the substrate (Figure 3). The spectrum of the multicomponent reflectance depends on the optical thickness of the layers in the model structure.

Generally speaking, the multi-layer structure amplifies the intensities of the reflected light with the specific wavelength whereas other wavelengths are suppressed due to the interference. The wavelength of the amplified intensity light depends on the thicknesses of the layers in the model structure. The model was described by the reflectance coefficient as a function of the wave amplitude. In this analysis the model was simplified by accepting a single layer antireflective structure with the zero extinction coefficient and the incident light perpendicular to the surface. In this case, the complex reflectance coefficient was described by the following equation:

Figure 3. Electromagnetic wave paths in double layer antireflective coating structure, where n_0 – air, n_1 – 2nd antireflective coating, n_2 – 1st antireflective coating, n_3 – substrate material.

$$r = \frac{r_1 + r_2 e^{-i\delta}}{1 + r_1 r_2 e^{-i\delta}}; \quad (2)$$

$$\delta = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} n d; \quad (3)$$

$$r_i = \frac{n_{i-1} - n_i}{n_{i-1} + n_i}. \quad (4)$$

Here r_1 and r_2 are the reflectances at the interfaces air/first film and the first/second film respectively. The reflectances are obtained from the Fresnel equations described by Eq. (4). The reflectance coefficient was obtained by multiplication of Eq. (2) with the complex conjugate. As a result it was obtained:

$$R = r r^* = |r|^2; \quad (5)$$

$$R = \frac{r_1^2 + r_2^2 + 2r_1 r_2 \cos \delta}{1 + r_1^2 r_2^2 + 2r_1 r_2 \cos \delta}. \quad (6)$$

Minimum condition was achieved when layer thickness and refractive index are:

$$d = \frac{\lambda}{4n_1}, \frac{3\lambda}{4n_1}, \frac{5\lambda}{4n_1}, \dots \quad (7)$$

$$n_1 = \sqrt{n_0 n_{Si}}, \quad (8)$$

where n_0 is real index of refraction of surrounding medium, where light comes from and n_{Si} – same thing for substrate (in this case silicon).

In double layer structure situation is far more complicated and reflection beam amplitude and reflection coefficient are as follows:

$$r = \frac{r_1 + r_2 e^{-i\delta_1} + r_3 e^{i(\delta_1 + \delta_2)} + r_1 r_2 r_3 e^{-i\delta_2}}{1 + r_1 r_2 e^{-i\delta_1} + r_1 r_3 e^{-i(\delta_1 + \delta_2)} + r_2 r_3 e^{-i\delta_2}} \quad (9)$$

$$R = \frac{r_1^2 + r_2^2 + r_3^2 + r_1^2 r_2^2 + 2r_1 r_2 \cos(\delta_1) + 2r_2 r_3 \cos(2\delta_1 + \delta_2) + 2r_1 r_3 \cos(\delta_1 + \delta_2) + r_1 r_2 r_3 (r_1 \cos(\delta_2) + r_2 \cos(\delta_2 - \delta_1) + r_3 \cos(\delta_1 + 2\delta_2))}{1 + r_1^2 + r_2^2 + r_3^2 + r_1^2 r_2^2 + r_1 r_2 \cos(\delta_1) + r_2 r_3 \cos(\delta_2) + r_1 r_3 \cos(\delta_1 + \delta_2) + r_1 r_2 r_3 (r_1 \cos(\delta_2) + r_2 \cos(\delta_2 - \delta_1) + r_3 \cos(\delta_1))} \quad (10)$$

Equation (10) shows that in DLARC structure reflectance is a complex function of material refractive index and layer thicknesses.

This particular structure contained textured surface plus absorption (instead of plain), therefore the "PV lighthouse" tool was used for the illustration of relation between refractive index and layer thicknesses with reflectance in more accurate way. In Figures 4, 5 and 7 relation between reflectance and refractive index can be analyzed. Full width at half maxima (FWHM) were calculated for two peaks of each curve with DLARCs with thicknesses of ITO: 100 nm and 200 nm and are shown in Table 1. Clear difference between ITO1 and both other (ITO2, ITO3) structures is visible. Sample with ITO1 has wider peaks and is characterized by refractive index that is higher than ITO2 and ITO3 and similar to that of SiN_x:H. This suggests that peak width can be narrowed for this particular structure if smaller refractive index values of ITO can be achieved.

Table 1. Full width at half maximum of reflectance spectra of 3 different antireflective structures: SiN_x:H/ITO1, SiN_x:H/ITO2, SiN_x:H/ITO3 with ITO thicknesses of 100 nm (Figure 4) and 200 nm (Figure 5).

	ITO thickness: 100 nm		ITO thickness: 200 nm	
	FWHM of Peak1	FWHM of Peak2	FWHM of Peak1	FWHM of Peak2
SiN _x :H/ITO1	63.22	309.27	45.15	110.6
SiN _x :H/ITO2	51.15	185.12	35.7	86.38
SiN _x :H/ITO3	59.13	225.05	42.27	92.13

A relationship between reflectance and ITO thickness (0, 50, 100, 150 and 200 nm) was shown in Figure 6. Peak of reflection shifts towards higher wavelengths (same peak was shown with an arrow on each curve), when ITO thickness is changed from 0 to 200 nm and second and even third peak appeared. The shape of spectrum of the reflected light resulted in the visual appearance of the multi-layer structure to an external observer (described in detail in the following section). The position of the highest maximum in Fig. 6 can be obviously associated with the dominant color in the visual appearance. Therefore the calculated curves in Fig. 6 explicitly demonstrated the relationship between the thickness of the oxide top layer and the color of the model cell.

Figure 4. Reflection curves of 3 different ITO/Si_x:H double layer antireflective structures with 100 nm ITO. Comparison of different ITO layers. Peaks: Peak1, Peak2 were used for FWHM calculations.

Figure 5. Reflection curves of 3 different ITO/Si_x:H double layer antireflective structures with 200 nm ITO. Comparison of different ITO layers. Peaks: Peak1, Peak2 were used for FWHM calculations.

Figure 6. Theoretical reflection spectra of solar cells with ITO/Si_x:H DLARCs and different ITO layer thicknesses: 0 (without ITO), 50, 100, 150, 200 nm (colors are approximate, adapted for those with impaired color vision).

Figure 7. Complex refractive indexes of ITO1, ITO2 and ITO3 layers used for simulation [23,24].

2.4 Appearance analysis in the CIE 1931 color space

In 1931 International Commission on Illumination (CIE) established the means for linking the visible spectra with the perceived colors of the human eye. The relationship is now called CIE 1931 XYZ color space. This space is illustrated in [Figure 8 \(b\)](#).

For the relationship between the incidence spectra and the perceived colors, the tristimulus values of X , Y and Z are calculated. Each of them represents response of different receptor cells of human eye that were defined by CIE as three color matching functions: $\hat{x}(\lambda)$, $\hat{y}(\lambda)$ and $\hat{z}(\lambda)$ ([Figure 8 \(a\)](#)). All of them together are now called a standard observer – a person with an average eyesight, described in the numerical representation. Tristimulus values X , Y and Z are calculated by integrating the result of multiplication of 3 spectra: reflectance or transmittance, irradiance of the source, response of receptor cells:

$$X = k \int_{\lambda_1}^{\lambda_2} I(\lambda) \cdot S(\lambda) \cdot \hat{x}(\lambda) d\lambda \quad (11)$$

$$Y = k \int_{\lambda_1}^{\lambda_2} I(\lambda) \cdot S(\lambda) \cdot \dot{y}(\lambda) d\lambda; \quad (12)$$

$$Z = k \int_{\lambda_1}^{\lambda_2} I(\lambda) \cdot S(\lambda) \cdot \dot{z}(\lambda) d\lambda; \quad (13)$$

$$k = \frac{100}{\int_{\lambda_1}^{\lambda_2} I(\lambda) \cdot \dot{y}(\lambda) d\lambda}; \quad (14)$$

and: $I(\lambda)$ – irradiance source ($W \cdot m^{-1} \cdot nm^{-1}$) (D65 illuminant is CIE standard for 6500 K light [25]), $S(\lambda)$ – reflected or transmitted spectra (nm^{-1}), $\lambda_1 \wedge \lambda_2$ are 380 and 780 nm respectively, covering entire photopic region.

Figure 8. CIE 1931 standard observer color matching functions for 10 deg. View (a). CIE 1931 color space chromaticity diagram (b).

The tristimulus values are often transposed into other

color spaces, as 3D space is not convenient for representation. One of examples is the xyY gamut, where the variables x and y are responsible for the chromacity (hue and saturation) and Y is responsible for the brightness. So this allows a depiction of the chromacity in a single xy plane, when Y is fixed. The variables x and y are related to the tristimulus variables by the following relationships:

$$x = \frac{X}{X + Y + Z}; \quad (15)$$

$$y = \frac{Y}{X + Y + Z}. \quad (16)$$

xyY space is designed in a way, that from the white point located in the center of fan shaped color space to the boundaries colors are getting more saturated (more pure) till at the edges they become monochrome [11].

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Solar cells with ITO/SiN_x:H DLARC

Solar cell structures with DLARCs were investigated, which have different ITO thicknesses. Images of typical series of samples (a set of color photographs of the front side of the cells.) are shown in Figure 9. A wide range of colors was obtained for both multicrystalline (a) and monocrystalline (b) cells. The difference in ITO layer thicknesses was about 9.25 nm between the adjacent samples in the series (according to calibration diagram in Figure 2). The differences were easily detected by a visual inspection of the sample surfaces as it can be seen in the color photographs in Figure 9.

Figure 9. (a) A series of the multicrystalline solar cell samples obtained from a commercial solar cell, for the rows and columns to the right and down: the ITO thickness increases gradually in the 9.25 nm step in the rows and from 18 nm to 185 nm in total through the columns down (the first one - dark blue - is the reference with 0nm ITO and the last one - brown - is exceptional with 240 nm thickness); (b) The monocrystalline solar cell samples with the ITO thicknesses: 102, 129, 46, 222 nm (up to down).

Simulation of solar cells with ITO/SiN_x:H DLARC was performed according to the description provided in Section 2.2. The parameters were selected for the SiN_x:H/ITO two-layer structure and the single SiN_x:H layer model. The thickness of the ITO layers was varied and current densities were calculated for the model and compared with experimental results. The simulation and experimental results are shown in Figure 10 and Figure 11 respectively.

Figure 10. Theoretical current density of SiN_x:H SLARC (purple) and 3 DLARC configurations: SiN_x:H/ITO1 (green), SiN_x:H/ITO2 (light blue), SiN_x:H/ITO3 (red). Negative thickness values depict SiN_x:H thickness and positive values depict ITO DLARC thickness (and SLARC).

Figure 11. Experimental current densities of monocrystalline and multicrystalline silicon solar cells with SiN_x:H/ITO DLARC.

The model samples with ITO1/ SiN_x:H and ITO2/ SiN_x:H were characterized by the current density values smaller to that of the ARC with only hydrogenized silicon nitride as a single layer antireflective coating (SLARC). The reason for the low current in the ITO1 samples can be associated with the real refractive index spectrum, which was very similar and a bit higher than that of the SiN_x:H (Figure 7), so making it act almost like as a single antireflective coating. In this way the light trapping

was not improved and similar or smaller current density values can be expected. The reason for the low current in the ITO2/SiN_x:H samples can be related to the optical characteristics and in particular to the imaginary part of complex refractive index. The ITO2 was characterized by the high extinction coefficient (marked as “k” in Figure 7) in the infrared region, so the absorption losses dominate versus more optimized light trapping. The ITO3 has much lower extinction coefficient and lower refractive index than the SiN_x:H and seems can be accepted being the optimal (for efficiency) for this particular structure based on the fact that the current density values are the highest.

Figure 12. Normalized current densities of experimental multicrystalline and monocrystalline values alongside with simulation results.

The theoretical curve for the ITO1/SiN_x:H had a minimum at about 139 nm thickness. These samples were characterized by the current density equal to 40.47 A/cm³. This was lower by about 5.95% compared to the samples without the ITO film. This configuration had the best agreement with the experimental results. For relative comparison, the normalized curves were graphically plotted in Figure 12. It followed from these figures that the theoretical and experimental results had the similar tendency for the both types of the samples, namely multi-crystalline and mono-crystalline cells.

The SiN_x:H/ITO3 current density curve in Figure 10 suggests that the ITO morphology, crystallography and stoichiometry can be further optimized for the light collection improvement. According to the simulation of SiN_x:H/ITO1 DLARC, which is in the best agreement with experimental results, refractive index and extinction coefficient values might be too high in this case (similar to that of SiN_x:H, Figure 7), that cause lower current density values than single layer antireflection coating. Besides, the imperfections of layers might be an additional factor.

As it has been explained and stated in section 2.2, numerical results presented in Figure 12, should considered as indicative and therefore calculated and measured data presented after the normalization.

3.2 Quantitative comparison of solar cell aesthetics in CIE xyY space

The CIE diagrams were constructed as a function of the ITO thickness and were presented in 13. The series of the samples with increasing thickness of the ITO films in DLARC structure were represented by dotted line (connecting data points) that can be traced in the area around that white point (being a D65 illuminant). The sample without ITO film is represented by white rectangle and it was accepted as the zero point in the diagram. The highest thickness value was indicated by the arrow in the CIE diagrams. According to the diagrams, the hues change with the increasing ITO thickness, until the highest ITO thickness was reached in this study. When comparing the simulation results in 13 (a) it can be accepted that the observed colors of the different ITO's seemed being very similar. Almost identical curves were obtained for the calculated 3 configurations, however a noticeable shift was

detected in the hues comparing the ITO1 with the both other samples. For the ITO2 and ITO3 samples, an increase in the thickness was followed by a slight shift of the ellipse like shape diagram curves towards the top of the fin shaped CIE space in Fig. 13. Considering the color, this shift means slightly purer blue and green colors of the cell surface. On the contrary, the orange, red and purple with all of the undertones became less clear. Besides, a comparison of the refractive indexes of the ITO1, ITO2, ITO3 and SLARC with the $\text{SiN}_x\text{:H}$ in Figure 7 suggests, that the smaller real refractive indexes were the main cause of such shifts of the ellipse like diagrams in this particular case.

Compared to the simulation, the experimental colors were less pure for all the samples and, especially, for the multicrystalline ones (13 (b), (c)). However, since in simulations an upward pyramid texture for Si substrate was used and since the texture shape for multi-Si is more complicated, direct comparison of the experimental and simulation results can't be performed for this case. Results of simulations can be used only for comparison with texture mono-crystalline Si substrate.

According to simulation colors should be more pure compared to experimental data for mono-Si cells (Figure 13 (a), (b)). Quite reasonable agreement can be seen in first half of an ellipse shaped curves in CIE diagram from 0nm ITO thickness (indicated as a white rectangle) towards yellow hues. However, with further increase of ITO thickness, higher discrepancies occur. This might indicate that the real texture shape is more complicated than the used theoretical approach. Detailed analysis of such discrepancies require morphology related studies of real texture solar cell structures, which is outside of the scope of this article.

Discrepancies between experimental mono and multi-Si cells can be associated with the morphology of differently textured multi-Si cells, consisting of crystalline grain matrix with various crystal orientations. Because of such structure multi cells are known to be acid textured to provide more uniform texturization, instead of alkaline texturization, which is common for mono-Si cells. As

a result, morphology of textured multi-Si samples is quite complicated and different, compared to that for mono-Si samples. As an example, Figure 14 shows experimental results for the reflectance of mono- and multi-Si solar cell structures with DLARC consisting of 46 nm ITO/SiN_x:H layer. From Figure 14 it can be seen that reflection peaks are wider for textured multi-Si based structures and moreover reflectance of multi-Si based structure is higher compared to the textured monocrystalline Si case, in the entire spectrum interval. This explains discrepancies in CIE diagrams between experimental mono and multi-Si cells in 13 (b), (c).

Figure 14. Reflectance of monocrystalline and multicrystalline silicon solar cells with 50 nm ITO on top of it.

This gives opportunity to customize specific type of cells to required aesthetic appearance. For example, the brown colors for the rooftops can be produced only by mixing the multiple colors, as monochrome brown color does not exist.

In 13 (c), the experimental results were shown for the reflectance of the PV module samples that were represented by the photographs in Figure 15. The arrows (blue for 0nm ITO and green for 185nm ITO) indicate the difference in the visual perception between the not encapsulated and the encapsulated cases. In the both cases it is a “big jump” towards the “white point” (D65 illuminant) between particular cases, meaning that the color after encapsulation becomes much less pure.

3.3 Solar module with ITO/SiN_x:H DLARC

The green and blue solar modules, that were produced using the multicrystalline solar cells without and with 185 nm thick ITO layer on the top, were visualized in Figure 15. The *I*-*V* curves obtained for these modules were shown in Figure 16 and the standard parameters of the modules were listed in Table 2. The results in Table 2 proved that there was a total 8.83% difference in the power between these two modules. The power was calculated from the formula:

$$P_{max} = V_{oc} I_{sc} FF. \quad (17)$$

In the green module, the power loss was mostly caused by the short circuit current (*I*_{sc}) (-3.54%), and the fill factor (FF) reduction (-4.73%), and only a small fraction of *V*_{oc} (-0.74%). This low influence of *V*_{oc} can be expected, as the ITO deposition was accomplished without interfering with the pn-junction of the cell.

Figure 15. Green (185 nm ITO) and blue (0 nm ITO) glass/glass solar modules with 6 sequentially connected cells.

Figure 16. IV measurement characteristics green and blue module with 0 and 185 nm ITO.

It should be noted that, the I - V curve and the fill factor values allowed to detect a decrease in the shunt resistance by almost 17% that can be an evidence of the conductive ITO layer causing some current flow via the edges of the cell. This suggests that a small frame must be left around the cell for insulation of the cell edges before the deposition of the ITO. Moreover, the series resistance of the green solar module did not show any charge collection improvement with an increase in the conductive area. It can be caused by much lower conductivity of the ITO films compared to the cell busbars.

Table 2. IV measurement characteristics of 0 and 185 nm ITO.

	V_{OC} , V	I_{SC} , A	V_{MAX} , V	I_{MAX} , A	P_{MAX} , W	FF, %	R , Ω	R_{SH} , Ω	Eff, %
Blue module	3.767	2.147	3.096	2.027	6.276	77.58	0.181	345.619	17.19
Green module	3.739	2.071	3.062	1.869	5.722	73.91	0.201	287.818	15.68
Difference	-0.74%	-3.54%	-1.10%	-7.79%	-8.83%	-4.73%	11.05%	-16.72%	-8.78%

3.4 Discussions

As it has been mentioned in the Introduction part, DLARC structures can be fabricated by implementation of different types of transparent oxides with appropriate optical parameters to

provide colorization of standard Si based solar cells with blue SiNx ARC. In particular, Al₂O₃ material has similar to ITO refractive index, and potentially can be used for fabrication of such DLARC. However, well known fact that Indium is rare and expensive metal, should be clarified for the case of ITO and Al₂O₃ (for a comparison) thin films. Important point here is that in case of the RF magnetron sputtered ITO/Al₂O₃ films relevant targets have to be used and cost of the deposited films is defined by the cost of such targets. From the comparison of quotations for identical (in terms of size and weight) ITO and Al₂O₃ targets it has been concluded that the cost of Al₂O₃ target is about 1.5 times higher than that for the identical size target from ITO. This conclusion can be explained by the fact that fabrication costs of the targets are different, and it is more expensive to sinter Al₂O₃ target from pure Al₂O₃ powder than similar target from Indium and Tin oxides. Since during RF sputtering, consumptions of such targets are comparable, it can be stated that cost of ITO deposited films are comparable (probably even cheaper) with the cost of thin transparent films from Al₂O₃.

In addition to the estimation of the cost related issues, the following potential advantages of ITO layers, as parts of DLAR coating for the cost-effective colorization of solar cells and relevant panels, should be mentioned:

- (i) in contrast to Al₂O₃ based coatings, ITO layers can be deposited using DC sputtering systems, which provides more flexibility for fabrication of DLARs using ITO.
- (ii) Large scale deposition of ITO layers on top of the glass based substrates to form IR reflective coatings for windows is a well-established technology by glass industry. Moreover, ITO layers currently widely used in most cases for different types of thin-film solar cells structures, as well as for Si based heterojunction solar cells. Therefore, industrial equipment and relevant optimized processes can be easily transferred to fabrication of the proposed DLARC structures.
- (iii) Deposition of an additional conductive ITO layer on top of Ag paste grids and busbars potentially can provide: (a) better charge collection in general and in the area of cracks, in particular, (b) reduce losses in the contacts of solar cells; (c) direct soldering of individual solar cells having DLARC during the assembly of PV modules, which is not possible for any other type of non-conductive parts of DLARC proposed for the colorization of solar cells in the literature. However, demonstration of such advantages requires special extended studies, which is out of scope of this article, since the main goal is to demonstrate cost effective approach for the colorization of industrial solar cells.

It should be also mentioned that alternative options, based on an implementation of other types of transparent oxides (TiO₂, SnO, ZnO, ZnO:Al, FTO, etc.) for fabrication of DLARCs can be considered as well. However, all these options require detailed analysis of the stability, up-scaling, technological optimizations, etc. while ITO based option is already well-established and approved in PV and in microelectronics technology and can be used without any complicated fabrication steps and modifications of the existing conventional technologies for Si based PV.

4. Conclusions

It is shown that the color of the commercial monocrystalline and multicrystalline solar cells can be effectively changed by simple room temperature magnetron sputtering deposition of an additional ITO film on the top of the commercially available Si based solar cells. At this stage of the

development it can be concluded that such colorization opens cost-effective option for the fast implementation of the proposed approach on industrial scale. It should be noted that any type of commercial solar cells can be colored individually in the same way. The changes in the visual perception of the color can be produced by an intentional change in the ITO film thickness, which can be achieved by variation and optimization of the deposition process parameters. The qualitative effect of the color modification can be checked by the CIE diagram.

Moreover, it was shown via simulations, that there was a significant impact on solar cell current density and only a slight shift in hues, between DLARC structures with different ITO's (with different refractive indexes). Although, lower refractive index was responsible for the much more narrow reflection peaks in the surface reflection spectrum, the resulting colors were only slightly shifted in appearance compared to the model.

The experimental and theoretical results of the current density, the analysis of the CIE color space and the module *I-V* characteristics suggested that the ITO films can be further improved for both visual appearance and optimal light trapping. The ITO's optical and electrical properties can be easily modified by intentionally changing the deposition conditions.

It is shown that the proposed color modification approach is applicable to the glass/glass module fabrication process. Mini-modules were fabricated using standard commercial multicrystalline cells and similar cells modified by deposition of 185 nm ITO. It is shown that efficiency of green module, fabricated using ITO/SiN_x:H DLARC is only about 1.5% lower than that for the mini-module manufactured using reference industrial cells with SiN_x:H ARC only. However, less pure colors were achieved for modules (indicated by CIE diagram), compared to non-encapsulated case.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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